

When Obstructive Jaundice Hides a Pulmonary Origin: Pancreatic Metastasis from Lung Cancer

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Abstract

Background: Pancreatic metastases are uncommon and may closely mimic primary pancreatic malignancies. Metastatic involvement of the pancreatic head by lung cancer is particularly rare and can present with obstructive jaundice, creating a major diagnostic challenge in patients with a previous thoracic malignancy.

Case presentation: A 63-year-old man with non-small-cell lung cancer treated one year earlier with concurrent chemoradiotherapy presented with progressive jaundice, generalized pruritus, dark urine, and pale stools. Laboratory investigations showed a cholestatic pattern. Ultrasonography demonstrated biliary duct dilatation without clearly identifying the obstructing lesion. Magnetic resonance imaging and magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography revealed a well-defined pancreatic head mass causing distal common bile duct compression and upstream intrahepatic and extrahepatic biliary dilatation. Endoscopic ultrasound-guided biopsy demonstrated tumor cells positive for thyroid transcription factor-1 and cytokeratin 7 and negative for cytokeratin 20, supporting a pulmonary origin. Whole-body positron emission tomography-computed tomography showed no other metastatic site, leading to the diagnosis of an isolated pancreatic metastasis from non-small-cell lung cancer. Endoscopic biliary stenting was performed, and the patient was referred for systemic palliative chemotherapy.

Conclusion: In patients with a history of lung cancer, a pancreatic head mass causing obstructive jaundice should not automatically be considered a primary pancreatic neoplasm. Magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography accurately defines the level of obstruction, but tissue sampling and immunohistochemistry are essential for establishing the origin and guiding appropriate treatment.

Keywords: *lung cancer; pancreatic metastasis; obstructive jaundice; MRCP; endoscopic ultrasound-guided biopsy; TTF-1*

INTRODUCTION

Secondary tumors of the pancreas are uncommon but clinically important lesions, particularly in patients with a known history of malignancy. Although renal cell carcinoma, melanoma, breast carcinoma and lung carcinoma may metastasize to the pancreas, pancreatic involvement by lung cancer remains rare in routine clinical practice and is frequently discovered incidentally during oncologic follow-up [1,2].

When a metastatic lesion is located in the pancreatic head, it may compress the distal common bile duct and mimic primary pancreatic adenocarcinoma, cholangiocarcinoma, ampullary tumor, or benign biliary obstruction. Obstructive jaundice caused by pancreatic metastasis from lung cancer is therefore an uncommon and potentially misleading presentation [3].

Cross-sectional imaging, and particularly magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP), plays a central role in identifying the level and mechanism of biliary obstruction. However, imaging alone cannot reliably determine whether a pancreatic mass is primary or metastatic. Tissue confirmation by endoscopic ultrasound-guided biopsy and immunohistochemical analysis is essential to establish the origin of the lesion and

guide appropriate oncologic management [4-6]. We report a rare case of pancreatic metastasis from previously treated non-small-cell lung cancer revealed by progressive obstructive jaundice.

Case presentation

A 63-year-old man with a history of non-small-cell lung cancer treated one year earlier with concurrent chemoradiotherapy presented with progressive jaundice, generalized pruritus, dark urine, and pale stools. There was no abdominal pain, fever, or recent weight loss.

On clinical examination, the patient was visibly jaundiced. Laboratory tests showed a cholestatic pattern, with elevation of total and direct bilirubin, increased alkaline phosphatase, and mildly elevated liver transaminases.

Initial abdominal ultrasonography demonstrated dilatation of the biliary ducts but did not clearly identify the cause of obstruction. A biliary MRI with MRCP was therefore performed. MRI revealed a well-defined mass centered in the pancreatic head, responsible for compression/stenosis of the distal common bile duct with upstream biliary dilatation (Figures 1-3). These findings raised the differential diagnosis of primary pancreatic malignancy versus pancreatic metastasis in the context of previous lung cancer.

To determine the exact nature of the pancreatic lesion, endoscopic ultrasound-guided biopsy was performed. Histopathological examination, including immunohistochemical staining, demonstrated tumor cells positive for thyroid transcription factor-1 (TTF-1) and cytokeratin 7 (CK7), and negative for cytokeratin 20 (CK20), supporting a pulmonary origin [6].

Whole-body PET-CT did not reveal any other metastatic site. Based on the clinical history, imaging findings, and immunohistochemical profile, the final diagnosis was isolated pancreatic metastasis from non-small-cell lung cancer. The patient underwent endoscopic biliary stenting for decompression and was referred to oncology for systemic palliative chemotherapy.

Discussion

Pancreatic metastases represent a diagnostic challenge because they may closely simulate primary pancreatic tumors on clinical and imaging grounds. In surgical and autopsy series, secondary pancreatic tumors are uncommon overall, but lung cancer is among the reported primary malignancies capable of involving the pancreas [1]. Maeno et al. described pancreatic metastases in a small subset of patients with lung cancer, most often as a solitary pancreatic nodule, although multiple nodules and diffuse pancreatic involvement may also occur [2].

Most pancreatic metastases from lung cancer are clinically silent and discovered during staging or follow-up imaging. Symptomatic presentation is less frequent and depends largely on lesion location. A mass in the pancreatic head may cause distal common bile duct obstruction, leading to jaundice, pruritus, dark urine and pale stools, as observed in the present case. This presentation is particularly deceptive because it overlaps with the typical clinical picture of pancreatic head adenocarcinoma [3,7].

The imaging work-up should start with ultrasonography, which is often useful to confirm biliary dilatation but may fail to identify the underlying cause. MRCP is particularly valuable for non-invasive mapping of the biliary tree, showing the level of obstruction, the degree of intrahepatic and extrahepatic duct dilatation, and the relationship of the mass to the distal common bile duct. In this patient, MRCP localized the obstruction to the pancreatic head and helped orient further diagnostic management.

Despite these advantages, radiologic features alone are insufficient to distinguish primary pancreatic cancer from metastatic disease. Pancreatic metastases may appear as well-defined masses and may be solitary, as in this case, but substantial overlap exists with primary pancreatic neoplasms. Therefore, in any patient with a

previous history of lung cancer and a newly discovered pancreatic mass, histological confirmation should be obtained before treatment decisions are made [4,5].

Endoscopic ultrasound-guided fine-needle aspiration or biopsy is a minimally invasive and highly useful method for obtaining tissue from pancreatic lesions. It enables cytological and histological assessment as well as immunohistochemical characterization. A TTF-1-positive, CK7-positive and CK20-negative profile strongly supports pulmonary origin in the appropriate clinical setting, and helps avoid misclassification as a primary pancreatic tumor [6].

Management depends on disease extent, tumor biology, performance status and control of the primary lung tumor. In most reported cases, treatment is palliative and combines biliary decompression with systemic therapy. Endoscopic biliary stenting rapidly relieves cholestasis and pruritus, prevents cholangitis, and allows subsequent oncologic treatment. Surgical resection may be considered only in highly selected patients with controlled primary disease and truly isolated pancreatic metastasis, but no standardized therapeutic strategy has been established [3,7].

Conclusion

Pancreatic metastasis from lung cancer is rare, and presentation with obstructive jaundice is even more unusual. In patients with a history of lung cancer, a pancreatic head mass causing biliary obstruction should not automatically be considered a primary pancreatic malignancy. MRCP is essential for anatomical assessment of the biliary obstruction, but definitive diagnosis relies on endoscopic ultrasound-guided tissue sampling and immunohistochemistry. Early recognition allows appropriate biliary decompression and avoids unnecessary surgical management when systemic treatment is indicated.

Declarations

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FIGURES

Figure 1: Axial biliary MRI image showing a well-defined mass centered in the pancreatic head, associated with upstream biliary duct dilatation.

Figure 2: Axial diffusion-weighted MRI image demonstrating a hyperintense pancreatic head lesion, suspicious for malignant involvement.

Figure 3: MRCP reconstruction showing dilatation of the intrahepatic and extrahepatic bile ducts with distal common bile duct obstruction at the level of the pancreatic head.

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